

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON MACHINE LEARNING ROLE IN GROUNDWATER QUALITY MONITORING

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Abstract

Groundwater contamination is a worldwide issue that significantly affects ecological services and human health. In the civil, industrial, and agricultural domains, groundwater is an essential resource. A third or so of the world's population gets their drinking water from groundwater. In arid and semi-arid locations with limited surface water and precipitation, groundwater is an especially valuable resource. One of the main factors influencing a country's ability to develop sustainably is ensuring a steady and renewable supply of groundwater for use. Planning, policy formation, and groundwater resource management all depend on the ability to predict groundwater pollution from various chemical components. However, urbanisation, industry, climate change, and agricultural activities pose a major danger to groundwater quality. Hazards to human health, ecological services, and sustainable socioeconomic development include hydrocarbons, hazardous metals, pesticides, trace organic contaminants, nanoparticles, micro plastics, and other newly discovered contaminants. The use of machine learning (ML) techniques to forecast groundwater quality (GWQ) has significantly increased during the last 20 years. This review is the most comprehensive contemporary review on the subject because it reviews all ensemble, semi-supervised, supervised machine learning and unsupervised machine learning models used to predict any parameter related to groundwater quality.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Groundwater quality, Groundwater Contamination.

1. INTRODUCTION

The environment is made up of several biotic and abiotic components such as food, water, air, and sunlight. For plants and animals to survive, water is essential. The most incredible, abundant, and useful material in the natural world is water. It is an all-purpose solvent and a renewable resource. Earth has a lot of water, yet only a meagre 0.33 percent of it is fit for human use. The remaining 99.67 percent is present in the oceans, aquifers, soils, and various icecaps; it is also floating in our atmosphere. A significant percentage is still unreachable, even with 0.33 percent accessibility.

Figure 1: Water Distribution on Earth[53]

Figure 1 shows the distribution of water on earth. Most of the water used by humans is obtained from hand pumps, rivers, lakes, tube wells, and other sources. Groundwater is the water found below the surface in soil pore, pores and permeable geological formations. An essential resource for agriculture, industry, and drinking is groundwater. The hydrological cycle depends on groundwater, which is necessary for wetlands and river flows. It supplies surface water systems with their foundational flow. Groundwater contains most of the freshwater on Earth that is not frozen [4,5]. Depletion and pollution of groundwater supplies are the issues. Groundwater will be impacted by climate change. Groundwater has a buffer capacity, which allows it to endure climate fluctuations. The water in the natural world contains a range of pollutants, each in varying degrees. Silt and other organic and inorganic pollutants are also carried by the water as it moves across the ground. Consequently, the runoff water contains a large number of pollutants. Artificial intelligence's machine learning (ML) field is highly skilled at creating prediction models from data. Machine learning uses inductive reasoning, as opposed to conventional approaches, to identify patterns and rules without the need for predefined equations. In both surface and groundwater resources, this method has demonstrated considerable potential in detecting underlying patterns and precisely forecasting water quality indicators. High-dimensional data and intricate, non-linear connections are easily processed by ML systems [6].

Figure 2: Machine Learning Market Size (2022-2028)

Data-driven machine learning techniques have significantly improved in performance thanks to recent developments in computer hardware and architecture, especially those tailored for machine learning and deep learning. These models are trained using common groundwater characteristics like Fluoride, pH, Na (Sodium) ,TDS (Total Dissolved Solids),Alkalinity ,Electrical conductivity, HCO₃ (Bicarbonate), CO₃ (Carbonate), and nitrate levels. Researchers can accurately anticipate and evaluate groundwater quality by examining different phases of the trained model [7, 8]. From 2023 to 2028, the machine learning market is projected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 44%, from USD 3101 billion in 2022 to USD 276.58 billion by 2028, as shown in Figure.2 (Source:-<https://www.stratviewresearch.com/2721/machine-learning-market.html>). This work presents a thorough assessment of machine learning in GW quality modelling, including a variety of forecasting approaches and contaminants.

1.1. An Introduction to the Methods and Procedures of Machine Learning

Iterative optimisation or closed-form solutions are two methods used to get the ideal set of parameters for prediction while training machine learning models. Many methods have been developed to improve the accuracy and performance of models. Figure 3 lists the various categories of machine learning methods. Reinforcement unsupervised and supervised learning. Careful selection of input data is crucial to reduce computational complexity and improve predictive capabilities [7]. To address the challenges of high-dimensional data, dimensionality reduction techniques can be employed to enhance similarity measurements. For specific tasks, feature learning can extract more effective input features. To prevent overfitting and improve model generalization, cross-validation is used, splitting data into training and validation sets. When dealing with limited data, data augmentation can artificially increase the training dataset size. The most popular optimization technique for differentiable functions is gradient descent, which seeks to minimize the loss function in order to get the optimal model parameters. Techniques for adaptive learning rates can improve the efficacy and efficiency of this optimization process. Figure 5 shows the ML modelling flow chart for clarity. Model selection comes after data splitting and pre-processing, according to the standard block diagram of machine learning models. After that, the chosen model is put through testing, validation, and training. To determine if the training model has achieved its objectives, cross-validation is employed. The model can then move on to testing and performance evaluation. If not, additional fine-tuning of the model parameters is required during training [8, 9].

Figure 3: Techniques Machine Learning

1.2. Machine Learning Role in Groundwater Quality Monitoring

By facilitating more precise forecasts, real-time analysis, and effective data processing of intricate hydrogeological factors, machine learning (ML) has become a potent instrument in the revolution of groundwater quality monitoring systems. Large amounts of multivariate water quality data, including physical, chemical, and biological characteristics, may be processed by these sophisticated algorithms to find trends, abnormalities, and possible contamination events that conventional monitoring techniques could overlook [14]. Groundwater quality indicators, such as pH levels, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and heavy metal concentrations, have been remarkably successfully predicted by a variety of machine learning (ML) techniques, including random forests, support vector machines (SVMs), and artificial neural networks (ANNs). Figure 6 shows the proportion of each form of machine learning used in this study to track the quality of the groundwater.

Additionally, in order to produce more accurate evaluations, ML models may take into consideration both geographical and temporal fluctuations in groundwater quality, taking into account elements like geological features, land use patterns, and seasonal variations. By using advanced imputation and outlier identification approaches, these algorithms also perform very well when managing missing or noisy data, which is a frequent problem in groundwater monitoring [16, 17]. In addition to saving time and money by automating the analysis of intricate hydrogeological datasets, machine learning (ML) improves the precision and dependability of water quality evaluations, which eventually leads to more efficient groundwater resource management and protection plans.

According to Figure 7, the application of machine learning methods for evaluating groundwater quality increased dramatically between 2015 and 2023, with supervised learning emerging as the most popular approach. According to the statistics, there was a noticeable increase in publications beginning in 2019, when there was more than twice as many researches than there were in 2018. The most notable rise was shown in deep learning applications, especially after 2020, which reflected the increasing complexity of neural network topologies in managing intricate groundwater quality factors. Unsupervised learning techniques grew moderately during this time, mainly in clustering applications for water quality classification, whereas hybrid learning techniques remained consistent but diminished [19,20]. The analysis of machine learning algorithms in groundwater quality monitoring, as shown in figure 8, demonstrates the application of multiple computational methodologies, each with a unique analytical purpose.

The most popular algorithms are Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), which are especially good at pattern identification and prediction tasks. The paper demonstrates the efficacy of ensemble techniques like as Gradient Boosting, Random Forest (RF), and Adaptive Boosting, which have shown exceptional resilience when working with intricate hydrogeological datasets. Hybrid systems that combine machine learning and conventional vulnerability assessment techniques, including DRASTIC-RF-SVM and DRASTIC-RF-MLP, show improved prediction accuracy. When modelling the correlations between several water quality measures, regression-based

approaches such as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Lasso Regression, Support Vector Regression (SVR), Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), and Multivariable Linear Regression work well. For classification problems, decision-based algorithms like Decision Trees, Classification and Regression Trees (CART), and Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) provide results that are easy to understand. While Logistic Regression (LR) works well for binary classification tasks in water quality assessment, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), and Multivariate Discriminant Analysis (MDA) offer flexible solutions for both classification and regression problems. The difficulty of monitoring groundwater quality and the requirement for specialised methods to handle different analytical issues are reflected in this varied algorithmic environment [38, 39].

1.3. Groundwater Quality and its Health Effects

The most important natural resource in the planet is groundwater, which is essential to maintaining ecosystems and conditions that support all life. Its uses are numerous and vital, ranging from commonplace ones like drinking, cooking, and bathing to more extensive ones in business and agriculture [24]. The quality of groundwater in emerging countries, however, is becoming a greater hazard to public health. This decline is mostly attributable to the population's explosive rise as well as the quickening pace of urbanisation and industrialisation. In several countries, groundwater quality degradation has become a serious problem, including Bangladesh, Iran, Pakistan, Bangladesh, China, and India. These countries are now facing serious problems with groundwater pollution, mostly as a result of fast growing densities, changing lifestyles, and shifting human behaviour. Particularly in India, the presence of several contaminants and falling groundwater levels pose a hazard to over 63% of districts.

Figure 4: Sources of Groundwater Contamination

The agriculture industry, which uses a lot of synthetic fertilisers and other unsustainable methods, is a major source of groundwater contamination in rural India and is a key contribution to this issue. Natural disasters and human activity are the two primary causes that primarily alter and impair groundwater quality. Although natural catastrophes may play a part, groundwater resource contamination is primarily the result of human activity. These man-made pollution sources are numerous and widely distributed. These comprise the following: the inappropriate removal of domestic waste from residential areas; the spilling of industrial wastewater onto public spaces; the seepage of dangerous materials from landfills; the occurrence of sewer system leaks; and the widespread use of artificial fertilisers and pesticides in agriculture.

These human-caused activities now rank among the main causes of the decline in groundwater quality, raising serious issues for the environment and public health [25, 26]. Figure 4 shows different sources of groundwater contamination. Groundwater pollution affects human health, the integrity of the ecosystem, and socioeconomic advancement, among other things. The dangers to one's health posed by excessive concentrations of metals, persistent organic pollutants, fluoride, and nitrate in groundwater have been the subject of several studies. Since babies and children are more susceptible to the impacts of these toxins than adults are, these concerns are more serious for them. The "blue baby syndrome" (infant methemoglobinemia) brought on by high nitrate levels and dental fluorosis (induced by high concentrations of fluoride above 1.5 mg/l) in drinking water used to prepare baby formula are two prominent instances of this sensitivity. Table 1 shows Major Contaminants affecting the quality of Groundwater and its health effects.

Table 1: Major Contaminants affecting Groundwater quality

Contaminants	Sources of Emission	Consequences
PH	Natural	Affects mucous membrane; bitter taste
Arsenic	Pesticides Improper waste disposal	Lack of energy weight loss. Skin and nervous system Toxicity
Turbidity	Industrial Activities	Cloudiness or haziness
Nitrate	Fertilizers House hold waste water	Blue baby disease in Infants
Chloride	Fertilizers Industrial waste	High BP
Fluoride	Industrial Waste Geological	Brownish discoloration of Teeth , bone damage ,skeleton damage
TDS	Nature of soil , Hazardous waste Minerals , Livestock waste	Undesirable taste; gastro intestinal irritations; corrosion or incrustation

Contamination of groundwater has an effect not only on direct consumption but also on the food production chain. Toxic components from heavy metals and persistent pollutants can build in crops when polluted groundwater is utilised for irrigation, posing a health risk to the food supply. Because agriculture, human health, and groundwater quality are all intertwined, it is imperative that clean groundwater supplies be preserved. Groundwater contamination is a global problem that has an impact on ecosystem functions and human well-being. Studies have continuously shown that chemical contaminants are a key problem in groundwater research over the past thirty years. Communities that depend on groundwater supplies are seriously threatened by this pervasive pollution. It does,

however, present scientists with a rare opportunity to study the evolution of subterranean water networks [27, 28]. It also presents a challenge to politicians to come up with plans for preserving the amount and quality of these essential water sources. By tackling this problem, we can safeguard the general public's health and learn important lessons about the intricate structure of aquifers. In order to maintain sustainable management of these vital resources, combating groundwater pollution ultimately necessitates a multidisciplinary strategy that combines scientific study with well-informed decision-making [33, 34].

2. RELATED WORK

Abbas et al., (2024) [1] offered a study that addresses the critical issue of groundwater quality evaluation by applying the Water Quality Index (WQI) to assess the suitability of water for drinking and agriculture. Recognising that traditional WQI calculations are time-consuming and prone to errors, the study offers a unique artificial intelligence (AI) prediction approach to increase accuracy and efficiency. Using 422 data samples, the study examined the WQI characteristics of the city of Mirpurkash in the Sindh province. To get a better knowledge of the dynamics of water quality, the research also looked at how different factors in the physiochemical examination of water interacted with one another. Several machine learning classifiers were used to predict WQI; Gradient Boosting and Random Forest performed better, with 96% and 95% accuracy, respectively. At 92%, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) showed the closest accuracy, followed by K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) at 84% and Decision Trees at 77%. Compared to conventional evaluation techniques, this AI-driven technology offers a considerable improvement and a possibly more accurate and efficient way to evaluate water quality. By including an uncertainty analysis utilising the R-factor, the research significantly increased its robustness and offered insightful information on the consistency and dependability of the predictions.

The combination of precise WQI prediction and uncertainty assessment increases the basis for groundwater utilisation decision-making processes and adds to a more thorough knowledge of the Mirpurkash water quality. Further investigations should concentrate on broadening the study's geographical reach, putting real-time data analysis into practice, incorporating newly emerging pollutants, creating user-friendly interfaces, investigating transfer learning for areas with limited data, evaluating the effects of climate change, contrasting AI predictions with conventional techniques, and incorporating the model into larger water management systems. The objective of these endeavours is to augment the AI model's relevance, precision, and pragmatic worth in transforming the assessment of water quality and environmental governance. **Zheng et al., (2024) [2]** proposed a study in Yopurga landfill site and other fast industrialising regions are prime examples of how severe water pollution is becoming and the need for more efficient techniques for monitoring and evaluating water quality has grown. In order to assess groundwater quality in a comprehensive manner in the vicinity of the Yopurga landfill, this study explores how the Water Quality Index (WQI) model can be integrated with state-of-the-art machine learning approaches. Three main components make up the research methodology:

choosing the right indicators for water quality, evaluating how well different machine learning algorithms (Xgboost, Random Forest, and Decision Trees) predict water quality, and figuring out which aggregation function works best for the WQI model. According to the study, the most significant indicators of water quality were manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni) and pH, and the Xgboost model fared better in this regard than other algorithms. It was found that the SWM (Simple Weighted Mean) model was the most suitable WQI model for this particular situation, and it showed that the general level of water quality in the region is between moderately and mildly contaminated. By illustrating the efficacy of fusing machine learning methods with conventional water quality assessment models, this study advances the field. It gives an approach that may be used in other comparable circumstances and a scientific basis for local initiatives to safeguard the water environment. Long-term monitoring, increasing indicators, cross-site comparisons, integrating geospatial data, predictive modelling, machine learning algorithm optimisation, improving stakeholder engagement, cost-benefit analysis, evaluating ecological impacts, and climate change adaptation should be the main areas of future research. By strengthening the integrated approach to water quality assessment and management's robustness and applicability, these initiatives would offer more thorough insights for environmental protection and policy-making.

Figure 5: Flow Chart of General Machine Learning Modeling

Sumdang et al.,(2023) [12] This study evaluates the possibility of arsenic poisoning in Thailand's Rayong coastal aquifers using machine learning methods, namely Random Forest, Artificial Neural Network and Support Vector Machine. The study examined data from 653 groundwater wells and used 27 field samples to validate the models. The algorithm Random Forest had the best performance and lowest uncertainty when compared to other algorithms in both shallow and deep aquifers. The generated risk maps show that there is a greater danger of arsenic contamination in the southern portion of shallow aquifers, which is correlated with the sites of industrial estates and landfills, and the northern section of deep aquifers. The study's creative application of machine learning has potential for determining pollution concerns and evaluating groundwater quality. Subsequent investigations may expand the scope of the model's utilisation by exploring other pollutants and regions to ascertain its adaptability.

Time-related data might make it possible to forecast trends in pollution over time, and adding more environmental and human-related variables could increase the accuracy of the model. Using IoT sensors with the RF model to create a real-time monitoring system might yield useful data for citizens and policymakers. Targeted interventions might also be guided by carrying out health impact evaluations in high-risk locations indicated by the model. Other areas of interest for the model are its capacity to study the long-term impacts of industrial development on groundwater quality and its utility in guiding policy decisions for sustainable groundwater management. All things considered, this research offers insightful information to citizens and legislators that will facilitate better groundwater resource management and public health protection. This unique technique has the potential to improve groundwater quality management worldwide by being applied to additional polluted aquifer studies. Such prediction techniques will become more and more crucial for sustainable water management and public health protection as urbanisation and industrialisation continue to put strain on groundwater supplies.

Mahboobi et al., (2023) [14] by looking at seven important variables— precipitation, slope, land use, groundwater depth, hydraulic conductivity, clay soil content, and distance to rivers—this study investigated the geographical variability in groundwater nitrate concentrations. To forecast nitrate concentrations in the Qom aquifer, the study used three machine learning (ML) models: Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest Regression (RFR), and K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) combined with Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR). The GWR-based ensemble strategy successfully accounted for geographical variability in the predictions, outperforming both individual ML models and traditional averaging techniques. The investigation found that northwest urban areas had the greatest levels of nitrate pollution, mostly as a result of insufficient sewage infrastructure and wastewater disposal through absorption wells. Due to their mostly agricultural and undeveloped land usage, the eastern and southeast areas, on the other hand, displayed lower pollution levels. To successfully control nitrate pollution, the study suggests extending urban sewage collecting systems and putting in place long-term groundwater monitoring. These results show that using GWR to incorporate local spatial linkages may greatly improve the accuracy of ML ensemble forecasts for evaluating groundwater quality. In order to create dynamic prediction models, future

research might include more environmental elements than the seven that were examined here, possibly including temporal fluctuations. Researchers may look at the use of more recent machine learning algorithms, including deep learning architectures made especially for spatial data, or more sophisticated spatial statistical techniques. Beyond nitrates, there is also the possibility of expanding this technology to other geographic areas and groundwater pollutants. The creation of real-time monitoring systems that use these ML-GWR models has the potential to completely transform groundwater contamination early warning systems. Future studies might also concentrate on developing tools that are easy to use for managers of water resources, automating the forecast process, and integrating scenarios related to climate change into the modelling framework. Furthermore, examining the long-term effects on groundwater quality and the economic viability of putting the suggested sewage system upgrades into practice might yield important information for environmental protection and urban planning regulations.

Banerjee et al., (2022) [18] presented a study forecasts temperature, pH, hardness, chlorides, turbidity, alkalinity, chemical oxygen demand, and dissolved oxygen, using four regression models: Support Vector Regression, Decision Tree Regression, Multivariable Linear Regression, and Lasso Regression. The dataset was pre-processed and split into training and test sets after being gathered through lab tests and field questionnaires. The study asserts that it is the first to link variables related to geography with the degree of water pollution. The authors claim that decision-makers in the field of water quality management may find value in their approach. The study offers a fresh method for predicting water quality by taking regional characteristics into account, which may provide insightful information. Because of its technique, which makes use of several regression models, comparative analysis and maybe more reliable results are possible. Ground surveys and laboratory testing are part of the data gathering process, which yields high-quality and trustworthy data. The study's emphasis on prediction as opposed to forecasting, meanwhile, could restrict how widely applicable it is. Future research into lead-time forecasts and soft computing techniques to enhance the water quality prediction is suggested by the authors. Although the research may help identify at-risk locations without requiring a lot of on-site testing, the summary doesn't make it obvious if the accuracy and dependability of the models were properly verified. To evaluate the study's generalisability, it is also necessary to take into account how well it applies to other geographical areas and water sources. Overall, this novel method of predicting the quality of water is promising, but more testing and investigation into its real-world uses would increase its influence.

Ijlil et al., (2022)[19] In this research five new ensemble/hybrid machine learning models developed for assessing groundwater contamination in Morocco's Saiss basin. A variety of machine learning methods, such as Random Forest (RF), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and two ensemble approaches—DRASTIC-RF-MLP and DRASTIC-RF-SVM—are used with the DRASTIC technique in these models. Several criteria, such as the ROC curve, accuracy, and precision, were employed to evaluate the models' effectiveness. The results show that when hybrid/ensemble machine learning approaches are used instead of separate ML algorithms, the performance is much

improved. The hybrid models demonstrated a significant improvement over the original DRASTIC technique, which had an AUC value of 0.51. With remarkable AUC values of 0.953 and 0.901, respectively, the DRASTIC-RF-MLP and DRASTIC-RF-SVM models were shown to be the best performers. DRASTIC-RF (0.852), DRASTIC-SVM (0.802), and DRASTIC-MLP (0.763) came next.

Figure 6: The proportion of publications on groundwater quality monitoring across all learning types

The study effectively pinpointed pollution-risk locations, emphasising those that need quick action and careful planning to improve the local population's quality of life and the environment. The study shows that by combining machine learning with the conventional DRASTIC approach, groundwater contamination assessment has advanced significantly. Although the study's findings are encouraging, especially given that the hybrid models have high AUC values; a few important issues need to be addressed. Questions concerning the validation procedure and possible overfitting are raised by the hybrid models' significant increase over the original DRASTIC method's AUC of 0.51 to values over 0.9. A more thorough description of the model validation procedures and data pre-treatment stages employed in the study would be beneficial.

Furthermore, despite the models' impressive performance measures, little attention has been paid to their computing costs, practical implementation difficulties, and scalability to different geographic areas. Information on these models' temporal stability and adaptability to shifting environmental variables is also lacking from the research. Furthermore, the study does not offer particular recommendations for intervention measures, which would increase its practical utility, even if it identifies sensitive locations. Notwithstanding these drawbacks, the study makes a significant addition to the technique of environmental assessment, especially in showing how well hybrid/ensemble approaches outperform standalone machine learning algorithms.

El Bilali et al., (2021) [20] In order to anticipate irrigation water quality indices utilising physical factors as inputs, this study investigates the application of artificial intelligence

models, which provide a practical and economical substitute for traditional techniques. Using electrical conductivity, temperature, and pH as input features, the research focusses on predicting several water quality parameters, including potential salinity, sodium adsorption ratio, total dissolved solids, magnesium adsorption ratio, exchangeable sodium percentage, and residual sodium carbonate. The study uses a dataset of 520 samples from the Berrechid aquifer in Morocco to apply and analyse four machine learning models: Random Forest, Adaptive Boosting, Support Vector Regression and Artificial Neural Network. The findings show that in terms of prediction accuracy, Random Forest and Adaptive Boosting models perform better than Artificial Neural Network and Support Vector Regression. The latter two models, however, show decreased sensitivity to input factors and improved generalisation ability. In general, the models that have been built have potential for predicting irrigation water quality indicators. This might help farmers and decision-makers manage irrigation methods in a more efficient and cost-effective manner.

This novel study, which has potential for underdeveloped nations, predicts complicated water quality indicators using physical factors. It contrasts many machine learning models and highlights the advantages and disadvantages of each. Further research might enlarge the dataset, include more parameters, provide intuitive user interfaces, integrate IoT devices, look at long-term dependability, carry out field validations, and study applications in diverse scenarios. Globally more sustainable irrigation techniques may result from these initiatives, which might improve machine learning's usefulness in managing water quality.

Singha et al., (2021) [22] this study analyses three machine learning (ML) models: eXtreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), artificial neural network (ANN) and random forest (RF). It also suggests a deep learning (DL) model. 226 groundwater samples were used in the study, which was carried out in the heavily agricultural Arang region of Raipur district, Chhattisgarh, India. Using a variety of physicochemical factors, an entropy weight-based groundwater quality index (EWQI) was calculated. Five error metrics were used to assess how well the models predicted the data. Outperforming the other ML models, the DL model achieves the maximum accuracy with a R^2 value of 0.996, while the other models perform worse, with R^2 values of 0.886, 0.927, and 0.917 for RF, XGBoost, and ANN, respectively. The performance of the DL model across several measures, including MSE, MAE, RMSE, RSR, NSE, and MAPE, further supports its supremacy. By repeating the method using randomised datasets, the study confirms the coherence of the DL model and finds only slight variations in performance measures. This research's thorough comparison of several ML models, which presents a distinct performance hierarchy of $DL > XGBoost > ANN > RF$, is one of its main advantages. The study also demonstrates how well the DL model can determine the importance of input factors in the EWQI calculation, indicating possible wider uses for the model in the evaluation and management of water quality.

The study does, however, have several shortcomings that may be fixed in further research. First off, because the study only uses one monsoon dataset, seasonal fluctuations in groundwater quality may not be captured. Future research should combine

many seasons' data to offer a more thorough knowledge of groundwater dynamics and better test the ML models' performance across diverse temporal settings. Additionally, even if the study shows how effective the DL model is in this particular situation, it would be beneficial to investigate its suitability in other hydrogeological and geographical contexts. This would support proving the generalisability and robustness of the model for broader use in the management of water resources. Additional hydro-geometeorological inputs might be integrated into the model in future study to improve its prediction power. This might include elements that, over time, may have a major impact on groundwater quality, such as variations in climate, land use, and precipitation patterns. The use of the DL model to forecast particular water quality parameters, such as biological oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and the elimination of significant pollutants like fluoride, nitrate, and potentially hazardous trace elements, is another exciting direction for future research. The model's use might be expanded in a way that would greatly benefit comprehensive plans for managing water quality.

Nafouanti et al., (2021) [23] this study highlights the costly and time-consuming nature of conventional groundwater quality analysis while addressing the important problem of groundwater fluoride pollution and the health hazards it poses. To forecast groundwater fluoride levels in the Datong Basin, the study uses statistical techniques, including Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The study intends to examine various statistical methodologies and determine the main factors influencing groundwater fluoride enrichment using 482 groundwater samples. The data was divided into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets as part of the technique, and the most pertinent variables were chosen using Chi-squared analysis. The optimal set of factors for predicting fluoride levels were found to include TDS, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, Na⁺, HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, K⁺, Zn, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺. The model's performance was evaluated using ROC (AUC) curves and confidence matrices. With an accuracy of 0.89, the results show that RF fared better than the other models, followed by ANN (0.85) and LR (0.76). The research area's groundwater fluoride levels are significantly influenced by eight out of the ten factors (K⁺ and Zn excluded), based on permutation feature analysis and mean decrease in impurity (MDI). The research exhibits proficiency in contrasting various statistical methodologies, using feature selection, and attaining elevated precision with the RF model. Geographical restrictions, a lack of temporal analysis, and a lack of geospatial data integration are some of the drawbacks, though. Expanding geographical breadth, combining temporal and geospatial studies, experimenting with ensemble approaches, examining the effects of climate change, creating user-friendly tools, contrasting with newly developed machine learning techniques, and analysing real-time monitoring systems should be the main areas of future research. Creating more adaptive and flexible models for a range of hydrogeological situations is the aim, which will eventually enhance the management of groundwater quality and safeguard public health.

Mosavi et al., (2020) [32] This ground-breaking work explores the application of machine learning (ML) models for forecasting groundwater hardness susceptibility, thereby addressing a major gap in the field of groundwater quality modelling research. The paper

assesses two ensemble models' efficiency in creating groundwater hardness susceptibility maps — Random Forest (RF) and Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)— against Multivariate Discriminant Analysis (MDA). The study classified water as hard or soft based on hardness ratings using information from 135 groundwater quality monitoring wells. The models included eleven predictor variables: evaporation (E), pH, precipitation (PCP), curvature, lithology, depth to groundwater (DTGW), land use, elevation, distance from the sea (DFS), and distance from the river (DFR). Important conclusions show that the modelling process was most significantly impacted by DFS, DTGW, elevation, and DFR.

Figure 7: Total numbers of studies of Machine learning in GWQ published each year by learning type

Low altitudes, shallow groundwater depths, and close proximity to rivers and oceans are all factors that promote the percolation of minerals containing magnesium or calcium into groundwater, and these characteristics have been linked to areas with high groundwater hardness. The work creatively uses comprehensive variables and efficient model comparison to apply ML approaches to groundwater hardness mapping. It provides useful information for managing water resources. Future research should concentrate on broadening the geographical scope, integrating temporal analysis, adding more variables, creating user-friendly tools, exploring transfer learning, developing real-time monitoring systems, examining relationships with other water quality parameters, and analysing the costs and benefits of preventive measures. This work makes a substantial contribution to modelling groundwater quality and offers useful tools for well-informed water resource management decision-making. **Knoll et al., (2019) [37]** The present work tackles the shortcomings of intricate hydro-biogeochemical models in creating management strategies for nitrogen input reduction by presenting a GIS-based statistical method for predicting nitrate concentrations in groundwater across wide regions. Four statistical models are compared in the study, which was carried out in the German state of Hesse: Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Boosted Regression Trees (BRT), Random

Forest (RF), and Multiple Linear Regression (MLR). These models investigate various designs of contributing regions (buffer zones) in order to maximise model performance. They use geographical environmental data and point nitrate concentrations as predictors. The Random Forest model outperforms the others, according to the analysis, with an R2 of 0.54. The percentage of arable land, hydrogeological units, and nitrogen balance are its primary determinants. The 1000 m circle contributing area utilised in this model best represents the area surrounding nitrate concentration monitoring stations. The primary advantage of the technique is its high applicability for regional-scale evaluations since it can forecast nitrate concentrations using just environmental characteristics that have been spatially mapped. The research demonstrates the potential of decision tree statistical models in integrating both numerical and categorical variables into a single prediction approach. A more thorough examination of the variables affecting groundwater nitrate concentrations is made possible by this flexibility. The study's methodology, which relies exclusively on spatial environmental predictors, represents a significant advance in predicting groundwater nitrate levels at a regional scale, offering improved transferability and applicability to areas lacking detailed point measurements. The report does, however, identify several shortcomings and potential topics for further research. The method ignores hydrochemical environmental elements in the groundwater body and locally unique groundwater flow conditions that might affect nitrate concentrations. Subsequent studies could concentrate on integrating these elements to improve model precision.

Figure 8: Machine learning algorithms used in this study

Predictive performance may also be enhanced by investigating methods for identifying the precise contributing region of monitoring sites using process-based representations of groundwater flow conditions. In order to evaluate the model's resilience and generalisability, future study may also entail investigating its application in other geological and geographical contexts.

In addition, combining environmental factors with the temporal dynamics of nitrate concentrations may provide light on long-term trends and seasonal fluctuations. Finally, examining how sensitive the model is to various geographical resolutions and considering the addition of more pertinent predictors might improve the model's prediction powers and increase the range of applications it can have in water resource management and policy-making.

Sajedi-Hosseini et al., (2018) [45] offers a unique framework that combines statistical, machine learning, and chemical analytical methodologies to evaluate the risk of nitrate groundwater pollution in dry locations. Using information from 102 wells, the study concentrated on the Lenjanat plain in Iran, producing maps of pollution incidence and likelihood. The likelihood of groundwater contamination incidence was predicted using three machine learning models: Boosted Regression Trees (BRT), Multivariate Discriminant Analysis (MDA) and Support Vector Machine (SVM).

A thorough probability map was then produced using an ensemble modelling technique. Using the Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUC) approach, the models' performance was verified. All three models contributed to the ensemble process by obtaining accuracy levels above 80%. The study's conclusions, which are consistent with current land use trends, show that the plain's centre parts are at high and extremely high risk of nitrate contamination. Decision-makers managing the risk of groundwater pollution can benefit greatly from this knowledge, particularly in semi-arid areas. In order to lessen groundwater pollution, the research highlights the significance of using less nitrogenous fertiliser and switching to more effective watering techniques, including drip irrigation.

The study offers a viable method for assessing the danger of groundwater pollution, but there are still a number of things that may be done better and in the future. First, in order to fully understand seasonal fluctuations and long-term trends in nitrate pollution, the research would benefit from a more thorough temporal analysis. Furthermore, include contaminants other than nitrates would give a more thorough picture of the region's problems with ground water quality.

Despite being novel, the study's dependence on machine learning models could make it less applicable in regions with less data. Subsequent investigations may examine methods to modify the structure for areas where data availability is sparse. To give a more comprehensive picture of the dangers associated with groundwater contamination in the future, socioeconomic variables and climate change estimates should also be added to the research.

The absence of a thorough cost-benefit analysis for putting the suggested mitigation measures into practice is another research gap. Future research, taking into account the possible effects on agricultural output and local life, should examine the financial viability of converting to drip irrigation and lowering fertiliser usage.

Lastly, while the study demonstrates the applicability of the ensemble modeling approach for regional-scale assessments, further research is needed to validate its effectiveness across different geographical and climatic contexts. This would demonstrate the robustness and generalisability of the methodology for use in groundwater contamination risk management on a worldwide scale, in order to forecast groundwater quality.

3. CONCLUSION

This thorough analysis shows how machine learning techniques have advanced significantly and been used more often in groundwater quality monitoring over the last ten years. According to the report, supervised learning algorithms—in particular, ANN, SVM, and RF—have taken centre stage in research because of their strong prediction powers and capacity to manage intricate hydrogeological data. By enabling real-time monitoring, early warning systems, and more accurate contamination forecasts, the use of machine learning has significantly increased the precision and effectiveness of groundwater quality evaluation.

The field's analytical skills have been further improved by the development of hybrid models and machine learning architectures, particularly when it comes to managing temporal and geographical fluctuations in water quality metrics. The study unequivocally demonstrates how machine learning algorithms have revolutionised conventional monitoring techniques by providing scalable, accurate, and reasonably priced groundwater quality management systems.

There are exciting opportunities for further study and development in the field of machine learning in groundwater quality monitoring. More effective real-time monitoring systems may be made possible by the combination of edge computing and machine learning models. More advanced deep learning architectures designed especially for hydrogeological applications have a lot of potential, especially when it comes to managing multi-dimensional data from several sensors and sources. In order to maintain stakeholder confidence and comply with regulations, future research should concentrate on creating more interpretable machine learning models that can offer insights into the decision-making process.

Data security and transparency in water quality monitoring might be improved by integrating block chain technology with machine learning algorithms. Furthermore, the problem of model adaption across various geographic locations and hydrogeological variables may be resolved by the development of transfer learning techniques.

Even with the notable progress, there are still a number of restrictions on machine learning applications in groundwater quality monitoring. The availability of complete, high-quality datasets required for training reliable machine learning models continues to be the

key obstacle. The generalisation capabilities of the models may be impacted by the fact that many of the current investigations depend on sparse temporal and geographical data. It can be difficult to justify and validate the judgements made by some sophisticated machine learning algorithms, especially deep learning models, due to their black-box nature. Additionally, there is a noticeable lack of uniformity in ML methodology among research, which makes it challenging to efficiently evaluate and assess various approaches. For small-scale monitoring activities, the computing resource requirements of complicated machine learning models may be prohibitive. Furthermore, models that are statistically correct but physically impractical might occasionally result from the failure to integrate conventional hydrogeological information with machine learning techniques. These drawbacks show how much more research and development is required to produce more useful, understandable, and economical machine learning methods for monitoring groundwater quality.

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